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“Emperor” Mu rug btsan and the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*

Brandon Dotson
School of Oriental and African Studies

Abstract: *Confusion shrouds the events surrounding the death of Emperor Khri Srong lde btsan (742-c. 800) and the succession of his sons at the turn of the ninth century. Tibetan religious histories, Old Tibetan sources, and Chinese sources offer conflicting pictures of the order of events and the identities of those involved. Fortunately, a newly published source, the 'Phang thang ma Catalogue, throws new light on the royal succession by referring to Mu rug btsan, the elder brother of Khri Lde srong btsan, as nothing less than an emperor (btsan po). Considering this new information alongside Old Tibetan inscriptional evidence, this article attempts to establish the order of events around Khri Srong lde btsan's abdication and death, and to locate "Emperor Mu rug btsan" within them.*

Introduction

The royal succession of the Tibetan emperors (*btsan po*) sets out the signposts for early Tibetan history and its periodization.¹ The order of succession is given in the *Royal Genealogy* (PT 1286), a document that properly forms a part of Tibet's first royalist epic history, the *Old Tibetan Chronicle*. The regnal dates are clear from the entries in the *Old Tibetan Annals*, which records the births, deaths, and enthronements of the Tibetan emperors with considerable precision. The yearly entries, however, only begin in earnest in 650, after the death of Khri Srong btsan, alias Srong btsan sgam po (d. 649), and end in the year 764, with a few entries missing in between. Therefore the regnal dates for those who ruled during the second half of the Tibetan Empire must be established with recourse to pillar edicts, other Old Tibetan documents, Chinese sources such as the *Tang Annals*, and post-dynastic Tibetan religious histories. Despite this relative abundance of sources

¹ Part of the research for this article was undertaken with the support of a Fulbright Grant to conduct research in China and Tibet. I here express my appreciation to the Institute of International Education for its support. I would also like to express my gratitude to Prof. Cristina Scherrer-Schaub, whose comments on an earlier draft of this article significantly improved its form.

through which to triangulate regnal dates, some tenacious problems persist unresolved. Notable among these are the dates for the birth and enthronement of Srong btsan sgam po and the names and dates of the sons and successors of Khri Srong lde btsan (742-c. 800). Here I will attempt to unravel the latter problem in light of a newly published source, the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*.²

The *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*

Before moving on to an examination of the problems surrounding the succession to Khri Srong lde btsan (742-c. 800), it will be useful to examine the nature of our newly published source, the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*. The *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* is one of the three catalogues of Buddhist texts compiled during the latter part of the Tibetan Empire. When Khri Srong lde btsan officially adopted Buddhism in c. 779, this emperor established official sponsorship for the support of such monasteries and temples as the Ra sa 'phrul snang (the Jo khang), the Ra mo che, Bsam yas Monastery, and Khra brug Monastery. The emperor also traveled with his own personal *samgha* at the Tibetan court.³ Further, this emperor established at the court a Buddhist council (literally, council of the representative(s) of the *bhagavat* at the court) and a committee for the translation of the *dharma*.⁴ This is evident from the Tabo fragments of the *Sgra sbyor bam po gnyis pa*, a document that formed part of a project to regulate and standardize the translation of Buddhist texts.⁵ In conjunction with this project, the Tibetan emperors sponsored

² Rta rdo, ed., *Dkar chag 'phang thang ma/ sgra sbyor bam po gnyis pa* (Beijing: Mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2003).

³ *pho brang 'khor gyi dge 'dun*. These circumstances are evident from Khri Srong lde btsan's *Bsam yas Edict*, preserved in the *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston* of Dpa' bo gtsug lag phreng ba (Dpa' bo gtsug lag phreng ba, *Dam pa'i chos kyi 'khor lo bsgyur ba rnam ky'i byung ba gsal bar byed pa mkhas pa'i dga' ston* [Beijing: Mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 1985], 372; *mKhas-pa'i-dga'-ston* by Dpañ-bo-gtsug-lag-phreng-ba, ed. Lokesh Chandra, *Satapitaka Series 9* [4] [New Delhi: International Academy of Indian Culture, 1965], 109b.3). For ease of reference, citations of this text employ both the Beijing edition (abbreviated as *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston B*) and the Delhi version (abbreviated as *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston D*).

⁴ *pho brang du bcom ldan 'das ky'i ring lugs [kyi mdun sa] dang / dar ma bsgyur ba'i lo cha pa'i sgra/*. This quotation is taken from the Tabo fragments of the *Sgra sbyor bam po gnyis pa*, which date to the reign of Khri Srong lde btsan (756-c. 797, c. 798-c. 800). The bracketed text, *kyi mdun sa*, is from a later version of the *Sgra sbyor bam po gnyis pa* assembled under Khri Lde srong btsan in 814. For a lexical comparison of this passage in both versions, see Jampa Panglung, "New Fragments of the sGra-sbyor bam-po gnyis-pa," *East and West* 44, no. 1 (1994): 170 and Cristina A. Scherrer-Schaub, "Enacting Words: A Diplomatic Analysis of the Imperial Decrees (bkas bcad) and Their Application in the sGra sbyor bam po gnyis pa Tradition," *Journal of the International Association of Buddhist Studies* 25, nos. 1-2 (2002): 288. The Tabo version dates to either 783 or 795, and the merit of these respective dates is discussed in Scherrer-Schaub, "Enacting Words," 289-92. The *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue* also attributes its compilation to the "council of the representative(s) of the *bhagavat* at the court" (*bcom ldan 'das ky'i ring lugs ky'i mdun sa*; Marcelle Lalou, "Les Textes Bouddhiques au temps du Roi khri-sron-lde-bcan," *Journal Asiatique* 241 [1953]: 319). The Old Tibetan text is only lightly edited here in order to retain the original orthographies, and corrections are offered only where the intended meaning is not readily apparent. In accordance with THDL and JIATS protocols, the reverse *gi gu*, which is commonly transliterated as a capital "I," is rendered as a lower case "i" preceded by a dash, i.e., "-i."

⁵ For an excellent overview of this project, see Scherrer-Schaub, "Enacting Words."

three catalogues of Buddhist texts, namely the *Lhan dkar ma Catalogue/Ldan dkar ma Catalogue*, the *Mchims phu ma Catalogue*, and the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*. The *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue* is found in the *Bstan gyur*, and has been studied by Lalou, among others.⁶ The other two catalogues, the *Mchims phu ma Catalogue* and the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, were long thought to have disappeared. Fortunately, however, the latter has recently come to light and was published in Beijing in 2003 together with a copy of the *Sgra sbyor bam po gnyis pa* from the Fifth Dalai Lama's library at 'Bras spungs Monastery.

In his recent treatment of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, Halkias demonstrates that the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* was compiled after the compilation of the *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue*.⁷ Specifically, Halkias claims that the compilation of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* commenced sometime during the reign of Khri 'U'i dum brtan (r. 841-42)⁸ or that of Khri 'Od srung (842/43-c. 890), but that it was "an open register which, being the last of its kind, was susceptible to scriptural augmentation yielding several variants from the second transmission of Buddhism (*phyi dar*) onwards."⁹ The late date of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*'s initial compilation is evident, Halkias notes, from the text's mention of Emperor 'U'i

⁶ Lalou, "Les Textes Bouddhiques."

⁷ Georgios Halkias, "Tibetan Buddhism Registered: A Catalogue from the Imperial Court of 'phang thang," *The Eastern Buddhist* 36, nos. 1-2 (2004): 54-55. Concerning the date of the *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue*, it was composed in a dragon year, when the court resided at Lhan dkar, which many scholars identify as 812. It is clear, however, that a later date cannot be ruled out, and indeed Yamaguchi dates its compilation to 824 (Zuiho Yamaguchi, "The Fiction of King Dar Ma's Persecution of Buddhism," in *De Dunhuang au Japon: Études Chinoises et Bouddhiques Offertes à Michel Soymié*, ed. Jean Pierre Drège [Geneva: Librairie Droz, 1996], 243 n. 15). The east inscription at Zhwa'i lha khang offers the strongest reason for abandoning 812 as the date of this catalogue, since this inscription is dated to "the benevolent later dragon year, when the court resided at 'On cang do" (*bka' drin 'brug gi lo phyi ma la/ pho brag 'on cang do na bzhugs pa '-i tshe/* [lines 22-23]; infra n. 39; Fang Kuei Li and W. South Coblin, *A Study of the Old Tibetan Inscriptions* [Taipei: Institute of History and Philology, Academia Sinica, 1987]). This corresponds to 812, and according to the imperial dating formula, which names the site of the court or council to distinguish one year in the twelve year cycle from another, this year would differ from the dragon year when the court resided at Lhan dkar whence the *Lhan dkar ma Catalogue* was compiled. This does not completely rule out 812 as the year of the *Lhan dkar ma Catalogue*'s compilation, however, as the royal court was stationed at different sites in summer and winter.

The Dunhuang document PT 1085 may in fact be the key for dating the dragon year of the *Lhan dkar ma Catalogue*'s compilation. PT 1085 is a response to the town prefect (*rtse rje*) of Sha cu, dispatched from the court at Lhan dkar in the middle winter month of the dragon year (*pho brag lhan kar nas// 'brug-i lo '-i dgun sla 'bring po '-i ngo la bkye 'i phyag rgya phogs te*; PT 1085, line 1). This is, no doubt, the same dragon year mentioned in the preamble to the *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue*. The reply from the court is "signed" by Minister Khrom bzher and Lha bzang gsas mthong (*blon khrom bzher dang / blon lha bzang gsas mthong g-i sug rgya 'og nas gthad*; PT 1085, lines 8-9). While the former name is too common to be of any use, the latter, once identified, may provide a clue concerning the date of this dragon year. For a further discussion of the date of the *Lhan dkar ma Catalogue*, see Halkias, "Tibetan Buddhism Registered," 48 n. 4, 51-54.

⁸ On the validity of these dates, see Yamaguchi, "The Fiction of King Dar Ma's Persecution," 250 and Yoshiro Imaeda, "Chinese Texts on the Tibetan King Glang Dar ma," *Bukkyō-gaku Seminā (Buddhist Seminar)* 74 (2001): 31.

⁹ Halkias, "Tibetan Buddhism Registered," 77.

Dum brtan, alias Glang dar ma.¹⁰ Under the misleading heading "commentaries on *sūtras* and *śāstras* by Khri Srong lde btsan,"¹¹ the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* lists texts attributed to emperors, queens, and monks.¹² Among these is "Emperor Dba' dun brtan's edict on Madhyamaka with accompanying commentary."¹³ "Emperor Dba' Dun brtan" is an obvious error for Dpal dum brtan. Remarkably, Yamaguchi, in reading a citation of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* by Bu ston, already noted the importance of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue's* attribution of this Madhyamaka commentary to 'U'i dum brtan: it indicates that "the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* must have been compiled after his reign."¹⁴ Indeed, unless we take this particular entry in the catalogue as a later addition – and there seems little or no reason to do so – this places the date of the catalogue's compilation in the reign of Khri 'U'i dum brtan or that of his successor, Khri 'Od srung, at the earliest. Assuming this to be the case, the earliest possible date for the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, compiled in a dog year, is 842. This does in fact harmonize quite well with what we know of 'Od srung, who resided in 'Phang thang for much of his reign, and eventually died there. Further, the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue's* attribution of a Madhyamaka commentary to Glang dar ma 'U'i dum brtan adds weight to the growing body of work that calls into question Glang dar ma's supposed opposition to Buddhism.¹⁵

Near the end of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, what might be called an appendix reveals the methodology by which the catalogue was assembled. This has already been discussed by Halkias, so I will only summarize briefly before moving onto a finer point.¹⁶ The heading of this section reads:

Sūtras and teachings whose titles do not quite correspond after comparison with three sources, but correspond in two sources, are mostly added to the ad hoc

¹⁰ Halkias, "Tibetan Buddhism Registered," 57-58.

¹¹ *mdo sde dang bstan bcas kyi ti ka/ btsan po khri srong lde btsan gyis mdzad pa/*.

¹² Rta rdo, *Dkar chag 'phang thang ma*, 54.

¹³ *btsan po dba' dun brtan gyi dbu ma 'i bka' bcad bshad pa dang bcas pa* (Rta rdo, *Dkar chag 'phang thang ma*, 57).

¹⁴ Yamaguchi, "The Fiction of King Dar Ma's Persecution," 243.

¹⁵ See Yamaguchi, "The Fiction of King Dar Ma's Persecution," Cristina A. Scherrer-Schaub, "Prières pour un apostat: fragments d'histoire Tibétaine," *Cahiers d'Extrême-Asie* 11 (1999-2000): 217-46, Samten G. Karmay, *Btsan po lha sras dar ma dang de'i rjes su byung ba'i rgyal rabs mdor bsdu* (Dharamsala: Library of Tibetan Works and Archives, 1986), and Samten G. Karmay, "King Lang Darma and His Rule," in *Tibet and Her Neighbours: A History*, ed. Alex McKay (London: Hansjörg Mayer, 2003), 57-66.

¹⁶ Halkias, "Tibetan Buddhism Registered," 75-76.

(*dkyus*)¹⁷ [catalogue]. Those that appear in one source, but not in two, are recorded elsewhere.¹⁸

The above passage reveals that the compilers of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* triangulated titles by comparing three main sources (*dpe*). The identity of one of these sources is revealed in the next sub-heading: “[titles] found in Bandhe Gzhon nu snying po’s source (*dpe*), but not found in the two old sources.”¹⁹ The other two sources are referred to as the “old sources,” and, given the late date of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, it is tempting to follow Halkias and understand these “sources” as none other than the *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue* and the *Mchims phu ma Catalogue*.²⁰ Such a conclusion may, however, be premature at present.

Gzhon nu snying po’s “source” is most likely a catalogue held by this Tibetan master. Fortunately, Gzhon nu snying po is mentioned in other Old Tibetan sources. IOL Tib J 689 (2), a Dunhuang document translated by Karmay, lists, by region, various lineages of *kalyāṇamitras* in Tibet.²¹ The first of these enumerates the “*kalyāṇamitras* of Bsam yas Monastery and ’Phrul snang upwards.”²² Famously, Lha lung Dpal gyi rdo rje, the supposed assassin of ’U’i dum brtan, fills the ninth place in this list, and this has prompted numerous scholars to regard him,

¹⁷ The term *dkyus* in the phrase *dkyus su sstal* is somewhat puzzling here, but the above reading can be confirmed with recourse to the *Sgra sbyor bam po gnyis pa*. The term usually means “race” or “crooked,” but the *Sgra sbyor bam po gnyis pa* states that when a new term is submitted for approval, once it is accepted by the council of the representative of the *bhagavat* at the court and the committee for the translation of the *dharmā*, it is added to the *dkyus/skyus* of the catalogue (*dkar chag gi dkyus su bsnan do*). Panglung (“New Fragments,” 165), presumably reading *dkyus* as *dkyus ma*, meaning “common” or “everyday,” translates *dkar chag gi dkyus* as the “general register.” This is plausible, but the grammar suggests that *dkyus* is a part of the catalogue, and not a description of it. While it is tempting to read this term as “appendix” or “addenda,” it is perhaps more prudent simply to understand *dkyus* as indicating an ad hoc catalogue, in this case of the holdings of the Tibetan court’s library of Buddhist texts, to which titles could be added at any time. The relationship between this ad hoc catalogue (*dkyus*) and the formal catalogues is uncertain. The former could be a sort of limbo for texts awaiting ratification. Another possibility is that the formal catalogues – the *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue*, *Mchims phu ma Catalogue*, and *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* – were the updated hand-lists of the Tibetan court’s holdings, named after the court sites at which the cataloguing was undertaken. The *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue*, *Mchims phu ma Catalogue*, and *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* would then be successive catalogues of the court library, or updated versions of essentially the same document. This would account for the fact that the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* contains nearly all of the texts listed in the *Ldan dkar ma Catalogue*, and is supported by the method of the catalogue’s compilation as described above. Skilling, it should be noted, already advanced the germ of such an interpretation (Peter Skilling, “From bKa’ bstan bcos to bKa’ ’gyur and bsTan ’gyur,” in *Transmission of the Tibetan Canon: Papers Presented at a Panel of the 7th Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies*, Graz 1995, ed. Helmut Eimer [Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 1997], 92).

¹⁸ *gsung rab mdo sde rnams kyi mtshan byang dpe gsum la gtugs nas nyung shas mi mthun pa dpe gnyis las mthun par ’byung ba rnams ni mang brtsan du byas nas dkyus su sstal/ dpe gcig las ’byung ste gnyis las ma byung ba rnams gud du bris pa/* (Rta rdo, *Dkar chag ’phang thang ma*, 49-50).

¹⁹ *dpe rnying rnams gnyis las ni ma byung / bandhe gzhon nu snying po’i dpe las byung ba/* (Rta rdo, *Dkar chag ’phang thang ma*, 50).

²⁰ Halkias, “Tibetan Buddhism Registered,” 75.

²¹ Samten Gyaltsen Karmay, *The Great Perfection: A Philosophical and Meditative Teaching of Tibetan Buddhism* (Leiden: Brill, 1988), 78-80.

²² *bsam yas dang ’phrul snang yan cad kyi dge ba’i shes nyen/*.

erroneously, as "the ninth abbot of Bsam yas Monastery." Less famously, Gle'u Gzhon nu snying po occupies the place immediately preceding as the eighth in the lineage of "kalyānamitras of Bsam yas Monastery and 'Phrul snang upwards."²³ As Karmay pointed out in his analysis of this list, it is a temporal lineage (*rgyud*), so it necessarily covers several decades. This fact, coupled with Gzhon nu snying po's proximity to Lha lung Dpal gyi rdo rje, places his tenure in the late part of the reign of Khri Gtsug lde brtsan (r. 815-41), which is to say approximately the mid-830s. Assuming that we are dealing with the same Gzhon nu snying po whose "source" was used for the compilation of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, we can locate this source temporally, and perhaps doctrinally as well, since Gle'u Gzhon nu snying po is also found in Gnubs Sangs rgyas ye shes's *Bsam gtan mig sgron* as the author of a meditation manual (*sgom lung*), or manual for "simultaneist" (*cig car ba*) meditation.²⁴

²³ The "office" of *kalyānamitra* is explained by a passage in Khri Lde srong btsan's *Skar chung Edict*, preserved in the *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston*, and in a nearly identical passage on the *Skar chung Pillar* itself (lines 33-43; Li and Coblin, *A Study of the Old Tibetan Inscriptions*, 319, 327). It is evident from this passage that the *kalyānamitra* is a privileged teacher of Buddhism, appointed as a personal "spiritual friend" to the emperor, and is above the rank of "representatives of the *bhagavat*" (*bcom ldan 'das kyi ring lugs*). Their geographical jurisdiction over Bsam yas Monastery and the Jo khang in IOL Tib J 689 (2) also indicates that those in this list had some authority at these places, but does not necessarily mean that they served as abbots. The passage from the *Skar chung Edict* in the *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston* is as follows:

The emperor's successors will appoint from among the monks *kalyānamitras* [to serve them] from their youth until they act as rulers. Whatever *dharma* one puts in his head, he should learn it, and all of Tibet should open the door to the study and practice of the *dharma*. Never will the door to liberation be blocked to the Tibetan subjects, from the upper classes on down, but the faithful will be established in liberation. Those among them who are able will be permanently appointed as representatives of the *bhagavat*. Never will those who act as representatives of the *bhagavat* and accord with the word of the teachings in all actions, and accord with the work and responsibilities of the teachings not be appointed to act as *kalyānamitras* (*btsan pho/ dbon sras sku chung ngur bzhugs pa yan chad/ chab srid kyi mnga' bdag mdzad pa man chad kyang dge slong las dge ba'i bshes gnyen bsgos te/ chos thugs su ci chud chud du bslab jing / bod yongs kyi kyang chos slob cing spyad pa'i sgo bead ste/ nam du yang bod ya rabs mand cad bod 'bangs las thard bar gzung ba'i sgo mi bgag par/ dad pa'i rnams las thar par btsud ste/ de'i nang nas nus pa las/ bcom ldan 'das kyi ring lugs rtag tu bsko zhing / bcom ldan 'das kyi ring lugs byed pa'i rnams/ chos 'khor nas bya'o cog gi bka' la yang gtogs te/ chos 'khor gyi las dang dbang byed cing / dge ba'i bshes gnyen byed par myi bsko re/ Dpa' bo gtsug lag phreng ba, Mkhas pa'i dga' ston B, 410-11; Mkhas pa'i dga' ston D, 129a.7-129b.3).*

See also the discussion of this term in Michael Walter, "The Significance of the Term *ring lugs*: Religion, Administration, and the Sacred Presence of the btsan-po," *Acta Orientalia Scientiarum Hungaricae* 51, no. 3 (1998): 312-13 n. 3.

²⁴ Karmay, *The Great Perfection*, 103. On the accuracy of "simultaneist" as a translation of *cig car ba*, as opposed to "instantaneist" or "subitist," see Rolf A. Stein, "Sudden Illumination or Simultaneous Comprehension: Remarks on Chinese and Tibetan Terminology," in *Sudden and Gradual: Approaches to Enlightenment in Chinese Thought*, ed. Peter N. Gregory (Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press, 1987), 41-66. That such strains of Buddhism persisted in Tibet long after the "Council of Tibet" is well known, and the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* also provides indirect iconographic evidence of this. On the first page of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* manuscript, the unknown redactor reveals that he made his copy from an illustrated manuscript. Among the captioned illustrations in the original, he states, were those of Nāgārjuna, Asaṅga, Vasubandhu, Candrakīrti, Śāntarakṣita, Kamalaśīla, Vimalamitra, Pad ma 'byung gnas, and "the great Chan teacher Hwa shang ma hwa ya na" (*bSam gtan gyi mkhan po chen po hwa shang ma hwa ya na*; Rta rdo, *Dkar chag 'phang thang ma*, 2), who was, of course, the famous representative of the "simultaneist" (*cig car ba*) tradition at the "Council of

Having discussed the nature of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* and demonstrated its source value, it is now possible to consider its contribution to the history of the royal lineage and the chronology of the succession after Khri Srong lde btsan.

Contributions of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* to the History of the Royal Lineage

The chronology of events during the reign of Khri Srong lde btsan poses some very important problems concerning the history of the Tibetan Empire. Chief among these are the dates for the foundation of Bsam yas Monastery, and the dates for the *Bsam yas Inscription* and the accompanying edicts preserved in the *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston*, as these announce the adoption of Buddhism as the official religion of Tibet. These are particularly difficult to determine because the two major sources for the history of the Tibetan Empire, the *Old Tibetan Annals* and the *Old Tibetan Chronicle*, both end during the first part of Khri Srong lde btsan's reign. Concerning the royal succession itself, the dates of Khri Srong lde btsan's death are also unclear, as are the regnal dates of his short-lived successor, Mu ne btsan/Mu ne btsan po. Many post-dynastic histories preserve a tradition according to which Khri Srong lde btsan abdicated in favor of his son, Mu ne btsan po.²⁵ This is most often reckoned to have occurred in 797. Khri Srong lde btsan's death is generally recorded shortly thereafter, and Mu ne btsan po is usually said to have reigned for less than two years.²⁶

The post-dynastic histories are hopelessly confused regarding the names of Khri Srong lde btsan's sons. In a long article, Haarh clarifies the tangle of names in post-dynastic histories.²⁷ As he points out, some of the most influential Tibetan histories, including the *Sba bzhed*, *Rgyal rabs gsal ba'i me long*, and the *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston*, contribute to the confusion surrounding this issue by using the name Mu tig btsan po to refer "more or less arbitrarily" to either of Khri Srong lde btsan's last two sons.²⁸ Subsequent scholars, both within and outside of Tibet, have repeated these errors. Relying mostly on a useful passage from U rgyan gling pa's *Rgyal po bka' thang yig*, Haarh reveals that Mu tig btsan po is none other than Khri Lde srong btsan, alias Sad na legs mjing yon.²⁹ This is, of course, the father of Khri Gtsug lde btsan, alias Ral pa can. Haarh concludes that Khri Srong lde btsan had four sons, the first being Mu khri btsan po, who died young. Despite the fact that this name is also conflated with those of the three later sons, Haarh argues that Mu

Tibet." The harmonious coexistence of these figures within the illustrated pages of a catalogue of Tibet's state-sanctioned Buddhism texts certainly indicates a milieu far more permissive of the "simultaneist" than that depicted in later Tibetan Buddhist historiography.

²⁵ Per K. Sørensen, *Tibetan Buddhist Historiography: The Mirror Illuminating the Royal Genealogies* (Weisbaden: Harrassowitz Verlag, 1994), 403 n. 1377.

²⁶ Sørensen, *Tibetan Buddhist Historiography*, 406 n. 1401.

²⁷ Erik Haarh, "The Identity of Tsu-chi-chen, the Tibetan 'King' Who Died in 804 AD," *Acta Orientalia* 25 (1960): 121-70.

²⁸ Haarh, "The Identity of Tsu-chi-chen," 149.

²⁹ Haarh, "The Identity of Tsu-chi-chen," 147-48.

khri btsan po is to be identified with the son whose birth is registered in the *Old Tibetan Annals*' entry for the mouse year 760.³⁰ The remaining three sons, according to Haarh, are Mu ne btsan po, Mu rug btsan po, and Mu tig btsan po, alias Khri Lde srong btsan, whose births he dates sequentially to the tiger, hare, and dragon years 774, 775, and 776.³¹ Haarh worked almost exclusively from post-dynastic histories, so these dates cannot be accepted with certainty. Employing Old Tibetan sources alongside the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, however, I will uphold Haarh's earlier conclusions regarding the names of Khri Srong lde btsan's sons.

The matter of the identities of Khri Srong lde btsan's sons is easily resolved in comparison to the problem of the events surrounding their royal succession. In his article devoted to the succession to Khri Srong lde btsan, Haarh attempted to harmonize post-dynastic Tibetan sources with a passage in the *Tang Annals* and other Chinese sources that recorded the death of a Tibetan emperor in 804. Haarh concludes that this reflected a struggle for succession between Mu rug btsan po and his younger brother Khri Lde srong btsan, and that the former, while not a legitimate emperor, was recognized by the Chinese as such.³² Consequently, Haarh argues, the Chinese sources that record the death of an emperor (*btsan po*) in 804 in fact refer to Mu rug btsan po.³³ Considering the evidence of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, and that of Old Tibetan sources, I will come to similar conclusions here.

The *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* demonstrates, in fact, that the Chinese were not alone in recognizing Mu rug btsan po/Mu rug btsan as emperor, but that he was recognized as such in Tibet as well. A fascinating entry in the section under the misleading heading "commentaries on *sūtras* and *śāstras* by Khri Srong lde btsan" records a commentary to the noble *Samdhinirmocanasūtra*, attributed to "Emperor Mu rug btsan."³⁴ While Mu rug btsan is mentioned in a pillar inscription at Zhwa'i lha khang as the elder brother of Khri Lde srong btsan, the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* is the only known Tibetan source that refers to him explicitly as an

³⁰ Haarh, "The Identity of Tsu-chi-chen," 149, 152. See also Jacques Bacot, Frederick W. Thomas, and Charles Touissant, *Documents de Touen-Houang Relatifs a l'Histoire du Tibet* (Paris: Librairie Orientaliste Paul Geuthner, 1940-1946), 58, 65.

³¹ Haarh, "The Identity of Tsu-chi-chen," 153.

³² Haarh, "The Identity of Tsu-chi-chen," 164-69.

³³ Haarh further argues that the struggle for succession was an expression of conflict between Bon po and Buddhist factions, but, due to the fact that this point rests on rather simplistic assumptions concerning "pre-Buddhist Bon religion" and "royal religion," I cannot support this conclusion. Indeed, while there is certainly continuity in terms of the practices of those ritual specialists known as *bon (po)* and *gshen* during the imperial period and some of the rites of the institutionalized Bon religion, particularly those of the first four of the nine vehicles, it has never been established with any certainty that "Bon" constituted a religion per se during the imperial period (though this depends in large part on what one means by "religion"). The role of *bon* and *gshen* in Old Tibetan ritual texts is taken up in detail in Brandon Dotson, "Complementarity and Opposition in Early Tibetan Ritual," *Journal of the American Oriental Society* (forthcoming).

³⁴ *'phags pa dgongs pa nges par 'grel pa'i mdo bshad pa btsan po mu rug btsan gyis mdzad pa/* (Rta rdo, *Dkar chag 'phang thang ma*, 55). This was also noted by Halkias ("Tibetan Buddhism Registered," 56-57), who further recognized its possible relation to the claim in Chinese sources regarding the death of a Tibetan emperor in 804.

emperor. Let us now consider this new evidence as it relates to what is known of the succession from Old Tibetan sources, turning first to inscriptional evidence.

The *Kong po Inscription* reveals that Khri Srong lde btsan ruled jointly with Lde srong, his chosen heir, who, when he took the throne, was known as Khri Lde srong btsan. This is evident from the fact that the inscription opens, “A decree granted to Rkong kar po during the reign of the divine emperor Khri Srong lde btsan and Lde srong, father and son” (lines 1-3).³⁵

The west inscription at Zhwa’i lha khang, which records grants made to Myang Ting nge ’dzin bzang po and his clansmen in recognition for their service to Khri Lde srong btsan, reveals that before Lde srong was enthroned as Khri Lde srong btsan there was friction between two parties, the one being Khri Srong lde btsan, and the other being Khri Lde srong btsan’s elder brother, Mu rug btsan, and that this was followed by a period of upheaval. Lines nine to twelve read:

Later, after the harmful struggle between my father and elder brother, at the time when I had not yet taken over the polity, there were also some who fomented disturbance and civil strife... (lines 9-12).³⁶

It is probably safe to assume that the dispute between Khri Srong lde btsan and his son concerned succession. The identity of this quarrelsome royal scion is made clear in lines 48-50 of the inscription, which lists some of those who swore to uphold the grants and privileges it records:

My elder brother Mu rug btsan, the royal ladies, minor kings, political ministers on downwards, and indeed all greater and lesser ministers swore an oath. The decree is given in perpetuity.³⁷

This passage further demonstrates that Khri Lde srong btsan ruled alone at the time of the inscription, and subordinated his elder brother Mu rug btsan, who, along with queens, minor kings (*rgyal phran*), and ministers, was bound by oath to uphold Khri Lde srong btsan’s edict.

By the time of the later, east face inscription at Zhwa’i lha khang, dated to “the later dragon year,”³⁸ there is no mention of Mu rug btsan. By naming a *later* dragon

³⁵ *lha btsan po khr-i srong lde btsan dang / lde srong yab sras ky-i ring la // // rkong kar po la gts-igs gngang ba //*. Li and Coblin, *A Study of the Old Tibetan Inscriptions*, 198, 205, 208.

³⁶ *// phyis yab dang gcen thugs nongs brud par byung ba ’i rjes // nga chab sr-id ma bzhes pa ’i skabsu kha cig phan phun dang / gdon stson pa dag yod pa yang /* (Li and Coblin, *A Study of the Old Tibetan Inscriptions*, 264, 276). My translation differs slightly from that of Li and Coblin. For comparison, see also Hugh E. Richardson, *A Corpus of Early Tibetan Inscriptions* (London: Royal Asiatic Society, 1985), 46-47. In both Li and Coblin’s translation and that of Richardson, “disagreement” is not strong enough for *thugs nongs*, which, while literally meaning “harming the mind,” can also indicate killing.

³⁷ *// gcen mu rug btsan dang / jo mo mched dang rgyal phran rnams dang / chab srid kyi blon po man chad / zhang lon che phra kun kyang mnas bsgags te / gts-igs g.yung drung du gngang ngo /*; Li and Coblin, *A Study of the Old Tibetan Inscriptions*, 266-67, 279-80. My translation differs slightly from that of Li and Coblin. For comparison, see also Richardson, *A Corpus of Early Tibetan Inscriptions*, 50-53.

³⁸ *’brug gi lo phyi ma*.

year, the dating formula of this later inscription does indicate, however, that Khri Lde srong btsan claimed the previous dragon year, 800, as part of his reign.³⁹ This does not necessarily indicate, however, that it was the first year of his reign.

The absence of Mu rug btsan in the later inscription at Zhwa'i lha khang might indicate that he was safely out of the picture by 812. Another inscription dating to the reign of Khri Lde srong btsan, however, predates this inscription, and makes no mention of Mu rug btsan. This is the *Ldan ma brag Inscription*, which dates to the monkey year 804.⁴⁰ This indicates that by the year 804, for reasons that are as yet unclear, Khri Lde srong btsan had no need to refer to or bind under oath his troublesome elder brother Mu rug btsan.

To summarize the inscriptional evidence, the *Kong po Inscription* and the inscriptions at Zhwa'i lha khang indicate that Khri Srong lde btsan ruled jointly with Prince Lde srong/Khri Lde srong btsan, and came into serious conflict with Lde srong's elder brother, Mu rug btsan. Khri Srong lde btsan then died, and sometime thereafter Lde srong was enthroned as Khri Lde srong btsan.

This picture is complicated somewhat by the presence in Old Tibetan sources of another one of Khri Lde srong btsan's brothers, Mu ne btsan. The *Royal Genealogy* (PT 1286) states that Khri Srong lde btsan and Lady Rma rgyal ldong skar of the Tshes pong clan bore the sons Mu ne btsan and Lde srong btsan, and that Mu Ne btsan's line was cut off (*gdung chad*).⁴¹ This official or quasi-official

³⁹ In fact, the passage refers to the "benevolent later dragon year" (*bka' drin 'brug gi lo phyi ma*, lines 22-23; Li and Coblin, *A Study of the Old Tibetan Inscriptions*, 271, 292). Li and Coblin translate this as "with regard to my grace, in the later Dragon year," but this is borne out neither by the grammar nor the punctuation. Richardson (*A Corpus of Early Tibetan Inscriptions*, 56-57) seems to have ignored the presence of *bka' drin* entirely in his reading of this passage. Intriguingly, the use of *bka' drin* here before a year in the reign of Khri Lde srong btsan mirrors the use of *skyyid rtags*, which in the *Lhasa Treaty Pillar* precedes dates during Khri Gtsug lde btsan's reign (East face inscription, lines 58, 62, and 65; Li and Coblin, *A Study of the Old Tibetan Inscriptions*, 51, 98-99). As has been noted before, "eternal happiness" (*skyyid rtags*) was the name given to Khri Gtsug lde btsan's reign, following similar Chinese practices (Li and Coblin, *A Study of the Old Tibetan Inscriptions*, 114). While this was thought to be the only instance of such a Tibetan regnal name, we should not discount the possibility that the reign of his predecessor, Khri Lde srong btsan, was referred to as the "reign of benevolence" (*bka' drin*).

⁴⁰ *spre'u gi lo'i dbyar/ btsan po khri lde srong btsan gy-i ring la/* (Chab spel tshen brtan phun tshogs, *Btsan po'i dus kyi brag brkos yig ris gcig gsar du mtshams sbyor zhus pa*, in *Bod kyi yig rnying zhib 'jug*, ed. Kha sgang bkra shis tshen ring [Beijing: Mi rigs dpe skrun khang, 2003 (1988)]). See also Yoshiro Imaeda, "Re-examination of the Ldan ma drag Inscription (II) in Eastern Tibet," in *Old Tibetan Studies Dedicated to the Memory of Professor Ronald E. Emmerick (1937-2001)*, ed. Cristina A. Scherrer-Schaub, *PLATS 2003: Proceedings of the Tenth Seminar of the International Association for Tibetan Studies, Oxford 2003* (Leiden: Brill, forthcoming). See, however, the 1998 addendum to an older article in Hugh E. Richardson, "More Early Inscriptions from Tibet," in *High Peaks, Pure Earth: Collected Writings on Tibetan History and Culture*, ed. Michael Aris (London: Serindia, 1998 [1988]), 278, where Richardson supports the later date of 816 for this inscription.

⁴¹ *khri srong lde btsan dang / tshes pong za rma rgyal ldong skar du bshos pa'-i sras/ mu ne btsan dang / lde srong btsan/ mu btsan gdung chad nas/* (PT 1286, lines 67-69). For the text, see Ariane Spanien and Yoshiro Imaeda, *Choix de documents tibétains conservés à la Bibliothèque nationale: complété par quelques manuscrits de l'India Office et du British Museum*, Tome 2 (Paris: Bibliothèque nationale, 1979), plate 556. For transliteration, see Yoshiro Imaeda and Tsuguhito Takeuchi, *Choix de documents tibétains conservés à la Bibliothèque nationale: complété par quelques manuscrits de l'India Office et du British Museum: Corpus syllabique*, Tome 3 (Paris: Bibliothèque nationale, 1990), 16. For

royal genealogy therefore indicates that Mu ne brtsan ruled as emperor between Khri Srong lde btsan and Khri Lde srong btsan. It says nothing, however, of Mu rug brtsan. What are we to make, then, of Mu rug brtsan's absence in this *Royal Genealogy* when the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* explicitly designates him as an emperor? First of all, the *Royal Genealogy*, as an official or semi-official document composed near to or after the collapse of the Tibetan Empire in the mid-ninth century, was an idealized lineage. This is not to say that the document is inaccurate or represents a whitewash, but only to point out that its imperative was to simplify the royal succession and emphasize the continuity of the royal line from its first mythical ancestor until the last emperor of royal blood. This genealogy, for example, does not mention Lha bal po, elder brother of Khri lde gtsug btsan (704-c. 754), who seized the throne for a short while after his father's death in 704, and was deposed in 705.⁴² While the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* was also an official document, sponsored by the Tibetan emperor, its compilers obviously felt no need to excise from the record a composition by Emperor Mu rug btsan, and in doing so they have handed down valuable information regarding the royal succession.

Taking into account the inscriptional evidence, the *Royal Genealogy* (PT 1286), and the evidence of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue*, the events surrounding the royal succession of Khri Srong lde btsan's sons seems to be as follows. Khri Srong

Bacot and Toussaint's transliteration and French translation, see Bacot et al, *Documents de Touen-houang*, 82, 89. See also Brandon Dotson, "A Note on Zān: Maternal Relatives of the Tibetan Royal Line and Marriage into the Royal Family," *Journal Asiatique* 292, nos. 1-2 (2004): 86-88.

⁴² The entry in the *Old Tibetan Annals* for the snake year 705 states, "At Pong lag rang, they deposed from the throne the emperor's elder brother, Lha bal po" (*pong lag rang du btsan po gcen lha bal po rgyal sa nas phab*; IOL Tib J 750, line 101). See Bacot et al, *Documents de Touen-houang*, 19, 40-41. Beckwith, who contends that the above passage should be read as indicating the deposition of Lha from Bal po, finds it likely that he was the son or relative of Princess Ga tun (meaning "princess" in Turkish), whose funeral is recorded in the winter of the snake year 708 (Christopher I. Beckwith, *The Tibetan Empire in Central Asia: A History of the Struggle for Great Power among Tibetans, Turks, Arabs, and Chinese During the Early Middle Ages* [Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1987], 73). Beckwith believes that Ga tun was a Western Turk princess, while Uebach extends the possibility that she was a daughter of the 'Zha Khagan (Helga Uebach, "Eminent Ladies of the Tibetan Empire According to Old Tibetan Texts," in *Les Habitants du Toit du Monde*, ed. Samten Gyaltsen Karmay and Philippe Sagant [Nanterre: Société d'Ethnologie, 1997], 59 n. 12). As Kapstein points out, the *Chos 'byung chen mo bstan pa 'i rgyal mtshan* by Lde'u jo sras (Lde'u jo sras, *Chos 'byung chen mo bstan pa 'i rgyal mtshan*, ed. Chos 'dzoms [Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 1987], 120) calls Lha bal po "the elder brother Lha bal po, child of the Pa tshab [lady]" (*gcen lha bal po pa tshab tsha*; Matthew T. Kapstein, *The Tibetan Assimilation of Buddhism: Conversion, Contestation, and Memory* [Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2000], 216). Whatever his actual parentage, it is evident that Princess Ga tun sent envoys to the Tang court requesting a bride, probably for Lha bal po (Christopher I. Beckwith, "The Revolt of 755 in Tibet," in *Contributions on Tibetan Language, History and Culture*, ed. Ernst Steinkellner [Wien: Universität Wien, 1983], 6 n. 8). With the deposition of Lha bal po, Ga tun's candidate lost out to the candidate of another royal lady, 'Bro Khri ma lod, who then ruled the country in the name of her grandson Rgyal gtsug ru/Khri Lde gtsug btsan. These events are reminiscent of the rivalry between the sons of Glang dar ma 'U'i dum brtan – 'Od srung and Yum brtan – over one century later. The possibility should thus not be discounted that the earlier rivalry between the two queens and their two candidates for the throne in the early eighth century served as a template for the muddled narrative of 'Od srung and Yum brtan in the mid-ninth century. Under the above circumstances, it is not at all surprising that Lha bal po, and indeed Mu rug btsan, were excised from the *Royal Genealogy* (PT 1286).

Lde btsan abdicated in favor of his son, Mu ne btsan.⁴³ Mu ne btsan then ruled for a short time before he died. Khri Srong lde btsan, like his ancestor, Srong btsan sgam po (d. 649), then retook the throne following the death of his son, and groomed his successor, Khri Lde srong btsan, with whom he ruled jointly. This upset Khri Srong lde btsan's elder son, Mu rug btsan, and serious conflict ensued. Khri Srong lde btsan died, and the two sons, Mu rug btsan and Khri Lde srong btsan, disputed the succession. Mu rug btsan briefly gained the upper hand and was recognized as emperor for a short period of time before Khri Lde srong btsan deposed him and took the throne. Mu rug btsan was at first subordinate to his younger brother, but subsequently disappeared from the picture. Further, it is quite possible, as argued by Haarh, that China recognized Mu rug btsan as emperor, and that it was his death that Chinese sources refer to in their accounts of the year 804.⁴⁴ It therefore seems likely that Mu rug btsan indeed ruled as Tibetan emperor for a short time before he was deposed by his younger brother, Khri Lde srong btsan.

While the order of events proposed above is quite likely, the chronology is less certain. There are two main problems with establishing a chronology, the first being the date of Khri Srong lde btsan's abdication and the rule of Mu ne btsan, as these dates are not found in Old Tibetan documents, and are therefore necessarily based on post-dynastic sources. The second problem concerns the dates for Emperor Mu rug btsan's reign. While in the later, east face inscription at Zhwa'i lha khang, dated to "the later benevolent dragon year" 812, Khri Lde srong btsan claims 800 as a year of his reign, he may well be discounting the reign of his usurper, and counting this as his own. That is to say, 800 is not necessarily the *terminus a quo* for Mu rug btsan's reign: he could have ruled at any time between Khri Srong lde btsan's death and 804, the likely year of his own death, but, as in the case of the official or semi-official *Royal Genealogy* (PT 1286), this would have been expunged from the official record.

Most post-dynastic sources agree that Khri Srong lde btsan abdicated in favor of Mu ne btsan po in 797. Of course, many of these sources also state that Khri Srong lde btsan died shortly thereafter, but the Old Tibetan sources demonstrate that these claims are mistaken. The early Sa skya histories, the *Bod kyi rgyal rabs* of Grags pa rgyal mtshan (1147-1216) and the eponymous work of 'Phags pa (1238-1280), both state that Khri Srong lde btsan died at age 56 in an ox year, and that Mu ne btsan po succeeded him for either one year and nine months or for two years.⁴⁵ Given that the *Old Tibetan Annals* records Khri Srong lde btsan's birth in 742, this would place his death in approximately 797. Other Tibetan histories, such as the *Rgya bod kyi chos 'byung rgyas pa* of Mkhas pa lde'u⁴⁶ and the *Mkhas pa'i*

⁴³ It should be noted that Richardson (*A Corpus of Early Tibetan Inscriptions*, 44) already advanced the first part of this hypothesis.

⁴⁴ Haarh, "The Identity of Tsu-chi-chen," 166.

⁴⁵ Guiseppe Tucci, "The Validity of the Tibetan Historical Tradition," in *Opera Minora*, ed. Guiseppe Tucci, vol. 2 (Roma: G. Bardi, 1971 [1947]), 456-57, 449.

⁴⁶ Mkhas pa lde'u, *Rgya bod kyi chos 'byung rgyas pa*, ed. Chab spel tshe brtan phun tshogs (Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 1987), 358.

dga' ston, state that Khri Srong lde btsan died at age fifty-nine, which corresponds to 800.⁴⁷ The newly published *Dbā' bzhed* states that Khri Srong lde btsan died in a horse year, which corresponds to 802.⁴⁸

Regarding the death of Mu rug btsan, later sources state that Mu rug btsan was killed by a member of the Sna nam clan in retribution for his murder of Sna nam 'U rings, son of Prime Minister Sna nam Rgyal mtshan lha snang.⁴⁹ This is also stated in the *Gsang ba phyag rgya can*, one of the five texts comprising the Can lnga, which were standard historical texts that Karmay dates to the late ninth or early tenth centuries.⁵⁰ There, however, Mu rug btsan is called Mu tig btsan po, underlining the confusion whereby the latter name is attributed sometimes to Mu rug btsan, other times to Khri Lde srong btsan.⁵¹

According to another tradition, found in Ne'u pañdi ta's *Chos 'byung me tog phreng ba*, Mu rug btsan became a monk after his murder of Sna nam Dbu ring. Further, this text also contains a tradition according to which Mu rug btsan – referred to here as Mu tig btsan po – built Khra sna Temple (*khra sna'i lha khang*). A gloss states that the temple is known as Nyams khru rnam dag gi gtsug lag khang, and that it was built by the divine emperor to expiate his sins from having killed Dbu ring. The text goes on to state that he also built Kong yul rkyang bu tshal Temple (*kong yul rkyang bu tshal gyi lha khang*) and became a monk.⁵²

Despite the ample evidence concerning the death of Mu rug btsan, including a royal tomb, Bhutanese tradition claims him as a protagonist in their hidden land

⁴⁷ Dpa' bo gtsug lag phreng ba, *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston* B, 405; *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston* D, 126b.5.

⁴⁸ Pasang Wangdu and Hildegard Diemberger, *dBa' Bzhed: The Royal Narrative Concerning the Bringing of the Buddha's Doctrine to Tibet* (Wien: Verlag der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 2000), 92-93 n. 359. In light of the *Dbā' bzhed*'s evidence, Wangdu and Diemberger (*dBa' Bzhed*, 93 n. 359) suggest that after Khri Srong lde btsan died in 802, Mu ne btsan po succeeded him, ruling until his death at the end of 803. It was this death, they suggest, that the Chinese sources record in 804. This would be a tidy solution to the problem of Khri Srong lde btsan's successors were it not for the fact that it ignores Mu rug btsan entirely. Further, it is untenable in light of the order of events determined above through an examination of Old Tibetan sources. The *Dbā' bzhed* is obviously confused, as Mu ne btsan po, who presides over his father's funeral in this text, was by this time dead. He appears to be conflated with Khri Lde srong btsan.

⁴⁹ Haarh, "The Identity of Tsu-chi-chen," 156-60.

⁵⁰ Samten G. Karmay, "The Origin Myths of the First King of Tibet as Revealed in the Can lnga," in *The Arrow and the Spindle: Studies in History, Myths, Rituals and Beliefs in Tibet*, ed. Samten Gyaltsen Karmay (Kathmandu: Mandala Book Point, 1998 [1994]), 307.

⁵¹ In fact, Dpa' bo gtsug lag, in a passage concerning the catalogues and the translation of Buddhist texts, cites Bu ston to the effect that the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* contains a commentary to the *Samdhinirmocanasūtra* not by Mu rug btsan, but by Mu tig btsan po (Dpa' bo gtsug lag phreng ba, *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston* B, 401; *Mkhas pa'i dga' ston* D, 124b.4). The *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* itself, as demonstrated above, reveals Dpa' bo's conflation of Mu rug btsan with Mu tig btsan po to be misleading.

⁵² *de'i gcung mu tig btsan pos khra sna'i lha khang snyams khru rnam dag gi gtsug lag khang zer bzhengs lha btsan pa* [read po] *dbu ring bsad pa'i sdig sbyongs/ rkang* [the editor corrects this to *kong*] *yul rkyang bu tshal gyi lha khang bzhengs nas rab tu byung ngo* / (Ne'u pañdi ta Grags pa smon lam blo gros, *Sngon gyi gnam me tog phreng ba*, in *Bod kyi lo rgyus deb ther khag lnga*, ed. Ldan lhun sangs rgyas chos 'phel [Lhasa: Bod ljongs bod yig dpe rnying dpe skrun khang, 1990], 23). The small text represents glosses, which appear in a smaller hand in the text.

(*sbas yul*) literature. According to this tradition, he is identified with Khyi kha ra thod (literally, "Dog mouth Goat skull"), the offspring of Tshes pong Bza' dmar rgyal's bestial liaison with a dog and a goat. Aris sees in Khyi kha ra thod an independent figure, whose lore grew to include Mu rug btsan and the much-maligned Queen Tshes pong Bza' dmar rgyal.⁵³ This may in fact have a historical basis, as the *Nyang ral chos 'byung* states that Mu rug btsan – referred to here again as Mu tig btsan po – returned from exile in Mon to take the throne after Mu ne btsan po's death. Upon arrival, however, he was killed by members of the Sna nam clan.⁵⁴ Mon, of course, is a vague toponym-cum-ethnonym that denotes the south, and often includes Bhutan and Sikkim.

Given this unruly tangle of dates to choose from for Khri Srong lde btsan's death, it seems better to return to the Old Tibetan sources for guidance. If we cautiously accept Khri Lde srong btsan's claim in the east face inscription at Zhwa'i lha khang that he ruled Tibet in the dragon year 800 (either jointly with his father or alone), we might propose the following tentative chronology. Following post-dynastic sources, Khri Srong lde btsan abdicated c. 797 in favor of his son, Mu ne btsan. Mu ne btsan then ruled for two years or less, c. 797-c. 798, before he died. Khri Srong lde btsan then retook the throne and ruled jointly with his chosen successor, Lde srong/Khri Lde srong btsan, c. 798-c. 800. This upset Khri Srong lde btsan's elder son, Mu rug btsan, and serious conflict ensued. Perhaps as a result of this conflict, Khri Srong lde btsan died, probably in 800 (i.e., at age fifty-nine as claimed in Mkhas pa lde'u's *Rgya bod kyi chos 'byung rgyas pa*). His two sons, Mu rug btsan and Khri Lde srong btsan, then disputed the succession in a contest that threatened to cause civil unrest. Mu rug btsan's brief ascendancy as emperor likely dates to c. 800-c. 802, shortly after Khri Srong lde btsan's death. Khri Lde srong btsan, with the help of powerful allies such as Myang Ting nge 'dzin bzang po, then gained the upper hand and retook the throne in c. 802, and Mu rug btsan died not long after, in c. 804.

While the order of events is established almost exclusively from the evidence of Old Tibetan sources, the chronology is less certain, and is meant only as a working hypothesis to help guide this problem to its final resolution. Besides resolving to a certain extent the succession at the turn of the ninth century, this proposed chronology also suggests dates for the *Kong po Inscription* and the west inscription at Zhwa'i lha khang. The former was erected when Khri Srong lde btsan ruled jointly with Lde srong, and therefore dates to c. 798-c. 800. The latter refers to a period in Khri Lde srong btsan's reign before the death of Mu rug btsan, and can therefore be placed between c. 800 and 804.

⁵³ Michael Aris, *Bhutan: The Early History of a Himalayan Kingdom* (Warminster: Aris and Phillips, 1979), 74-75.

⁵⁴ "Then they invited Mu ne btsan po, who had been in exile in Mon, and enthroned him. The Sna nam clansmen said, 'if you do this...' and as soon as he exposed his breast, they killed him" (*de nas mu tig btsan po mon na spyugs te yod pa khong la dbang bskur bar chad byas te spyan drangs pa dang / sna nam pas 'di byed na zer te/ mu tig btsan po 'i brang kha bye nas krongso/*; Nyang nyi ma 'od zer, *Chos 'byung me tog snying po sbrang rtsi'i bcud*, ed. Chab spel tshe brtan phun tshogs [Lhasa: Bod ljongs mi dmangs dpe skrun khang, 1988], 414).

Conclusions

Among the considerable contributions of the *'Phang thang ma Catalogue* to our understanding of the Tibetan Empire, it adds another fold to the issue of the royal succession at the turn of the ninth century by designating Mu rug btsan as an emperor. Adding this new data to what we already know about the succession from pillar edicts and Old Tibetan texts such as the *Royal Genealogy* (PT 1286), the matter now seems somewhat closer to resolution. To summarize, the proposed order of events (along with a tentative chronology) is as follows:

- c. 756-c. 797 First reign of Khri Srong lde btsan.
- c. 797-c. 798 Reign of Mu ne btsan.
- c. 798-c. 800 Second reign of Khri Srong lde btsan; rules jointly with chosen successor Lde srong/Khri Lde srong btsan.
- c. 800-c. 802 Mu rug btsan seizes throne from Khri Lde srong btsan upon the death of their father, Khri Srong lde btsan.
- c. 802-c. 815 "Second" reign of Khri Lde srong btsan; Mu rug btsan is subordinate to his younger brother, then dies c. 804.

When further documents come to light and provide authoritative dates for the death of Khri Srong lde btsan and the activities of Mu rug btsan, the chronology proposed above may require slight alterations. I can only hope that further ancient sources, such as the *Mchims phu ma Catalogue*, will soon emerge and shed even more light on such issues.

Glossary

Note: glossary entries are organized in Tibetan alphabetical order. All entries list the following information in this order: THDL Extended Wylie transliteration of the term, THDL Phonetic rendering of the term, English translation, equivalents in other languages, dates when applicable, and type.

Ka					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>kong po</i>	Kongpo				Place
<i>kong yul rkyang bu tshal gyi lha khang</i>	Kongyül Kyangbutselgyi Lhakhang	Kongyül Kyangbutsel Temple			Temple
<i>dkyus</i>	kyü	ad hoc			Term
<i>bka' drin 'brug gi lo phyi ma</i>	kadrin drukgi lo chima	the benevolent later dragon year			Term
<i>rkong kar po</i>	Kong Karpo				Person
<i>skar chung</i>	<i>Karchung</i>				Text
<i>skyyid rtags</i>	kyitak	eternal happiness			Term
Kha					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>khyi kha ra thod</i>	Khyikha Ratö	Dog mouth Goat skull			Person
<i>khra sna 'i lha khang</i>	Trané Lhakhang	Trana Temple			Temple
<i>khra 'brug</i>	Tradruk				Monastery
<i>khri lde gtsug btsan</i>	Tri Detsuktzen			704-c. 754	Person
<i>khri lde srong btsan</i>	Tri Desongtsen				Person
<i>khri gtsug lde brtsan</i>	Tri Tsukdetsen			r. 815-41	Person
<i>khri 'u'i dum brtan</i>	Tri Üdumten			r. 841-42	Person
<i>khri 'od srung</i>	Tri Ösung			842/43-c. 890	Person
<i>khri srong lde btsan</i>	Tri Songdetsen			742-c. 800	Person
<i>khri srong btsan</i>	Tri Songtsen				Person
<i>khrom bzher</i>	Tromzher				Person
<i>mkhas pa lde'u</i>	Khepa Deu				Author
<i>mkhas pa 'i dga' ston</i>	<i>Khepé Gatön</i>				Text
Ga					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>ga tun</i>	Gatün				Person
<i>gi gu</i>	gigu				Term
<i>grags pa rgyal mtshan</i>	Drakpa Gyeltsen			1147-1216	Person
<i>glang dar ma</i>	Langdarma				Person
<i>glang dar ma 'u'i dum brtan</i>	Langdarma Üdumten				Person

<i>rgya bod kyi chos 'byung rgyas pa</i>	<i>Gyabökyi Chöjung Gyepa</i>				Text
<i>rgyal po bka' thang yig</i>	<i>Gyelpo Katang Yik</i>				Text
<i>rgyal phran</i>	gyeltren	minor kings			Term
<i>rgyal rabs gsal ba'i me long</i>	<i>Gyelrap Selwé Melong</i>				Text
<i>rgyal gtsug ru</i>	Gyeltsukru				Person
<i>rgyud</i>	gyü	temporal lineage			Term
<i>sgom lung</i>	gomlung	meditation manual			Term
<i>sgra sbyor bam po gnyis pa</i>	<i>Drajor Bampo Nyipa</i>				Text
Ca					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>can lnga</i>	Chengnga				Text Group
<i>cig car ba</i>	chikcharwa	simultaneist			Term
<i>bcom ldan 'das kyi ring lugs</i>	chomdendekyi ringluk				Term
<i>bcom ldan 'das kyi ring lugs kyi mdun sa</i>	chomdendekyi ringlukkyi dünsa				Term
Cha					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>chos 'byung chen mo bstan pa'i rgyal mshan</i>	<i>Chöjung Chenmo Tenpé Gyeltsen</i>				Text
<i>chos 'byung me tog phreng ba</i>	<i>Chöjung Metok Trengwa</i>				Text
<i>mchims phu ma</i>	<i>Chimpuma</i>	<i>Mchims phu ma Catalogue</i>			Text
Ja					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>jo khang</i>	Jokhang				Monastery
Nya					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>nyang ral chos 'byung</i>	<i>Nyangrel Chöjung</i>				Text
<i>nyams khros rnam dag gi gtsug lag khang</i>	Nyamtrü Namdakgi Tsuklakkhang				Monastery
Ta					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>bstan 'gyur</i>	Tengyur				Textual Collection
Tha					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>thugs nongs</i>	tuknong	lit. "harming the mind"; harmful; to die			Term

Da					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>gdung chad</i>	dungché				Term
<i>ldan dkar ma</i>	<i>Denkarma</i>	<i>Ldan dkar ma Catalogue</i>			Text
<i>ldan ma brag</i>	Denma Drak				Place
<i>lde srong</i>	Desong				Person
<i>lde srong brtsan</i>	Desongtsen				Person
<i>lde'u jo sras</i>	Deu José				Author
Na					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>ne'u pañdi ta</i>	Neu Pendita				Author
<i>gnubs sangs rgyas ye shes</i>	Nup Sanggyé Yeshé				Author
<i>sna nam</i>	Nanam				Clan
<i>sna nam rgyal mtshan lha snang</i>	Nanam Gyeltsen Lhanang				Person
<i>sna nam dbu ring</i>	Nanam Uring				Person
<i>sna nam 'u rings</i>	Nanam Uring				Person
Pa					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>pad ma 'byung gnas</i>	Pema Jungné				Person
<i>pong lag rang</i>	Ponglakrang				Place
<i>dpa' bo gtsug lag phreng ba</i>	Pawo Tsuklak Trengwa				Author
<i>dpal dum brtan</i>	Peldumten				Person
<i>dpe</i>	pé	source			Term
Pha					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>pho brang 'khor gyi dge 'dun</i>	podrang khorgyi gendün				Term
<i>phyi dar</i>	chidar				Term
<i>'phags pa</i>	Pakpa			1238-1280	Author
<i>'phang thang</i>	Pangtang				Place
<i>'phang thang ma</i>	<i>Pangtangma</i>	<i>'Phang thang ma Catalogue</i>			Text
<i>'phrul snang</i>	Trülning				Monastery
Ba					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>bandhe gzhon nu snying po</i>	Bandhé Zhönnu Nyingpo				Person
<i>bal po</i>	Belpo				Place
<i>bu ston</i>	Butön				Person
<i>bod kyi rgyal rabs</i>	<i>Bökyi Gyelrap</i>				Text
<i>bon</i>	Bön				Organization; Term

<i>bon po</i>	Bönpo				Organization
<i>dba' dun brtan</i>	Wa Dünten				Person
<i>dba' bzhed</i>	Wazhé				Text
<i>dbu ring</i>	Uring				Person
<i>'bras spungs</i>	Drepung				Monastery
<i>'brug gi lo phyi ma</i>	drukgi lochima				Term
<i>'bro khri ma lod</i>	Dro Trimalö				Person
<i>sba bzhed</i>	Bazhé				Text
<i>sbas yul</i>	beyül	hidden land			Term
Ma					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>mu khri btsan po</i>	Mutri Tsenpo				Person
<i>mu tig btsan po</i>	Mutik Tsenpo				Person
<i>mu ne btsan</i>	Muné Tsen				Person
<i>mu ne btsan po</i>	Muné Tsenpo				Person
<i>mu ne brtsan</i>	Muné Tsen				Person
<i>mu rug btsan</i>	Muruksen				Person
<i>mu rug btsan po</i>	Muruk Tsenpo				Person
<i>mon</i>	Mön				Place
<i>myang ting nge 'dzin bzang po</i>	Nyang Tingngedzin Zangpo				Person
<i>rma rgyal ldong skar</i>	Magyel Dongkar				Person
Tsa					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>btsan po</i>	tsenpo	emperor			Term
<i>rtse rje</i>	tsejé	town prefect			Term
Tsha					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>tshes pong</i>	Tsepong				Clan
<i>tshes pong bza' dmar rgyal</i>	Tsepong Zamargyel				Person
Zha					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>zhwa'i lha khang</i>	Zhé Lhakhang				Temple
<i>gzhon nu snying po</i>	Zhönnu Nyingpo				Person
'a					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>'u'i dum brtan</i>	Üdumten				Person
<i>'od srung</i>	Ösung				Person
<i>'on cang do</i>	Önchangdo				Place
Ya					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>yum brtan</i>	Yumten				Person

Ra					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>ra mo che</i>	Ramoché				Monastery
<i>ra sa 'phrul snang</i>	Rasa Trülñang				Monastery
<i>ral pa can</i>	Relpachen				Person
Sha					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>sha cu</i>	Shachu				Place
<i>gshen</i>	shen				Term
Sa					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>sa skya</i>	Sakya				Organization
<i>sad na legs mjing yon</i>	Senalek Jingyön				Person
<i>srong btsan sgam po</i>	Songtsen Gampo			d. 649	Person
<i>gsang ba phyag rgya can</i>	<i>Sangwa Chakgyachen</i>				Text
<i>bsam gtan mig sgron</i>	<i>Samten Mikdrön</i>				Text
<i>bsam yas</i>	Samyé				Monastery
Ha					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>hwa shang ma hwa ya na</i>	Hwashang Mahayana				Person
<i>lha bal po</i>	Lhabelpo				Person
<i>lha bal pho</i>	Lhabelpo				Person
<i>lha bzang gsas mthong</i>	Lhazang Setong				Person
<i>lha lung dpal gyi rdo rje</i>	Lhalung Pelgyi Dorjé				Person
<i>lhan dkar</i>	Lhenkar				Place
<i>lhan dkar ma</i>	<i>Lhenkarma</i>	<i>Lhan dkar ma Catalogue</i>			Text
A					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Other	Dates	Type
<i>u rgyan gling pa</i>	Urgyen Lingpa				Person
Sanskrit					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Sanskrit	Dates	Type
			<i>Asaṅga</i>		Person
			<i>bhagavat</i>		Term
			<i>Candrakīrti</i>		Person
			<i>dharma</i>		Term
		spiritual friend	<i>kalyāṇamitra</i>		Term
			<i>Kamalaśīla</i>		Person
			<i>Madhyamaka</i>		Doxographical Category
			<i>Nāgārjuna</i>		Person

			<i>Samdhinimocanasūtra</i>		Text
			<i>saṃgha</i>		Term
			<i>sūtra</i>		Term
			<i>Śāntarakṣita</i>		Person
			<i>śāstra</i>		Term
			<i>Vasubandhu</i>		Person
			<i>Vimalamitra</i>		Person
Chinese					
Wylie	Phonetics	English	Chinese	Dates	Type
			<i>Chan</i>		Organization
			<i>Dunhuang</i>		Place

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PT 1085. A response to the town prefect (*rtse rje*) of Sha cu.

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IOL Tib J 750. The second part of the *Old Tibetan Annals*, "civil version."

Kong po Inscription. Concerns privileges of the land of Kong po, and dates to c. 798-c. 800.

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